

The Contamination Lab as a Possible Pathway to Make Agricultural Engineering Raise its Academic Prominence and Centrality in Italian Academia: Insights from a Case-Study

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Abstract

Italian Agricultural Engineering, while evolving toward the broader, inter-disciplinary field of Biosystems Engineering (which includes also the study of biomasses/biomaterials, field mechanization in difficult contexts and advanced post-harvest agri-food technologies), suffers from a structural critical issue due to its historical academic placement within the Agricultural rather than the Engineering Departments. This peripheral positioning limits the depth of the technical subjects proposed to the students, does not facilitate the necessary collaboration with core engineering disciplines in the research and didactics activities, thereby potentially slowing innovation in crucial fields like agro-bio-energies, precision agriculture and field robotics. To address this misalignment and foster inter-departmental synergy, this study proposes adopting the Contamination Lab (C-Lab) model as the archetype of a possible framework of academic and professional networking involving the Agricultural Engineering. C-Labs (transdisciplinary platforms proposed by the Italian Ministry of University and Research, MUR) function as experiential laboratories, gathering students from Engineering, Agronomy, Computer Science, and Economics to collaboratively develop solutions to real-world challenges posed by industry stakeholders. The integration of a permanent, thematic C-Lab focused on agri-forestry and food machinery, supported by methodologies for enhancing creativity in technical fields, such as the Design Thinking, represents an effective (and necessary) strategy to make Agricultural Engineering recover a higher visibility on the Italian (and international) scenario and, in prospect, relocate it the at the centre of any research involving the technological and technical aspects of agriculture, forestry and food. It is concluded that this initiative can serve as an institutional bridge for hybrid training, which is essential for aligning academic competencies with the growing demands for innovation and multidisciplinary professionalism in the national agrifood-tech sector.

Keywords

Agricultural Engineering, Biosystems Engineering, Contamination Lab (C-Lab), Multidisciplinarity, Hybrid Training, Agrifood-tech, Agricultural and Forest Mechanization, Food Machinery, Structural Criticality in University Education.

1. Introduction

1.1 The Agricultural Engineering: ambit and declination of this subject in Italy

Agricultural Engineering today is increasingly recognized as a specialized branch within the broader and rapidly evolving domain of Biosystems Engineering, an interdisciplinary field that integrates engineering principles with biological and environmental sciences to develop sustainable solutions for living systems (AgriSTUFF, 2025; ASABE, 2025a) (Fig. 1). Biosystems

54 Engineering encompasses a wide range of applications, including agricultural production, food
55 and biomass processing, environmental protection, energy systems, and the management of
56 natural resources (AgriNext Conference Team, 2024; Foppa-Pedretti et al., 2010; Jongebreur &
57 Speelman, 1997). Within this framework, Agricultural Engineering maintains its historical identity
58 focused on the mechanization and optimization of agricultural practices and technologies, while
59 simultaneously contributing to broader biosystemic goals such as climate-smart agriculture,
60 circular bioeconomy, highly-efficient bioprocessing industry and ecosystem resilience (Bietresato
61 & Mazzetto, 2018). The evolution from Agricultural to Biosystems Engineering reflects a
62 paradigmatic shift from sectoral problem-solving toward systems-oriented innovation,
63 acknowledging the complexity and interdependence of biophysical, technical, and socio-
64 economic processes (Aguado et al., 2011; ASABE, 2025b; Briassoulis et al., 2008; CIGR -
65 International Commission of Agricultural and Biosystems Engineering, 2025; Dokmen & Aslan,
66 2016; Febo & Comparetti, 2013). As such, Agricultural Engineering serves both as a foundational
67 component and as a practical interface of Biosystems Engineering, particularly in the design,
68 implementation, and dissemination of technological innovations for agri-food, forestry, and rural
69 systems (ASABE, 2025a).
70

71
72 **Figure 1.** Topics composing the UniMAP's Biosystems Engineering Programme
73 (School of Bioprocess Engineering, 2012).
74

75 The Agricultural Engineering, as an academic and professional discipline, encompasses the
76 application of engineering principles to agricultural and forestry production systems, post-harvest
77 (food-)processing chains, and rural infrastructures, with the overarching aim of enhancing
78 productivity, sustainability, and technological innovation across agri-food and bioresource
79 sectors.

80 In Italy, the field has evolved in close connection with the country's diverse agro-ecological
81 regions, particularly within Mediterranean and Alpine contexts, requiring site-specific
82 mechanization strategies and technological responses (Pellizzi, 2000; Santini, 2025). The Italian
83 declination of Agricultural Engineering, named "Agricultural Mechanics" since its first apparition
84 in the academia, dated back to 1870 in Milan, 1875 in Portici - Napoli (Santini, 2025), includes
85 not only conventional areas such as mechanical power generation and delivery, tillage, seeding,
86 irrigation, and harvesting, but also significantly incorporates forest mechanization and post-
87 harvest processing technologies (Bietresato & Mazzetto, 2018). Forest mechanization—ranging
88 from timber harvesting to transportation and biomass handling—has assumed increasing
89 importance in the Italian context, especially in mountainous and fragile territories where complex
90 terrain morphology necessitates specialized equipment. Forestry machines such as cable
91 yarders, harvester-forwarder systems, and slope-adapted multifunctional tractors are widely
92 studied within national research initiatives, particularly through collaborations involving CREA

93 (Consiglio per la Ricerca in Agricoltura e l'Analisi dell'Economia Agraria) (Magagnotti & Spinelli,
94 2011). The emphasis is placed on low-impact and high-efficiency operations that align with
95 national forestry strategy and EU Green Deal priorities.

96 Simultaneously, machines and equipment used in post-harvest processing and food industry
97 applications represent a cornerstone of Agricultural Engineering (Bhooshan et al., 2024),
98 especially in Italy. These systems include machinery e.g. for processing (i.e., cleaning, drying,
99 grading, pressing, fermenting, milling), and packaging a wide spectrum of agricultural
100 commodities, and products derived from them—from grains and fruits to oils, juices and wines.
101 Beyond product preservation and food safety, these technologies are designed to ensure energy
102 efficiency, process traceability, and environmental compliance under circular economy principles
103 (Zhang et al., 2022). Significant attention is also devoted to the engineering of systems for by-
104 product valorisation and industrial symbiosis.

105 Academically, these domains are addressed within the Italian university system under the
106 coordination of the “*Associazione Italiana di Ingegneria Agraria*” (AIIA, 2025) and formally
107 categorized under the scientific-disciplinary sector “AGRI-04/B” (formerly “AGR/09”) “*Meccanica
108 Agraria*” (Agricultural Mechanics) (Comparetti et al., 2005), part of the Academic Recruitment
109 Field “07/AGRI-04” (formerly “07/C1”) “*Ingegneria Agraria, Forestale e dei Biosistemi*”
110 (Agricultural, Forest and Biosystems Engineering), in turn part of the Area 07 “*Agricultural and
111 Veterinary Sciences*”, as defined by the Italian Ministry of University and Research (MUR -
112 Ministero dell'Università e della Ricerca, 2024). Italian curricula in the field “07/AGRI-04” reflect a
113 system-oriented and interdisciplinary philosophy, which integrates mechanization, process
114 engineering, and environmental management to address the complex needs of the agri-food and
115 forestry sectors.

116 However, the teaching of Agricultural Engineering and its subdomains in Italy faces considerable
117 structural and institutional challenges, requiring prompt answers, no longer subject to
118 postponement. One of the most critical issues lies in the disciplinary placement of these subjects.
119 Unlike in many other countries—such as Germany, the United States, or the Netherlands—where
120 Agricultural Engineering is institutionally embedded within the Schools of Engineering, in Italy it
121 is historically placed within Departments of Agricultural Sciences and related subjects (e.g.,
122 Environmental, Food, and Animal Sciences). Just to state the misalignment of Italy with most of
123 the other countries, ASABE, i.e. probably the most important international association for
124 Agricultural and Biological Engineering (founded in the USA, with members from 100 countries)
125 (ASABE, 2025b), of which many Italian researchers in Agricultural Engineering are part, is one of
126 35 professional societies that comprise ABET, i.e. the Accrediting Board for Engineering and
127 Technology, primarily in the United States, but expanding across the globe (ABET, 2021). The
128 Italian legacy, rooted in post-war agricultural development policies (Vaquero Piñeiro, 2024), has
129 resulted in Agricultural Engineering (and related subjects) nowadays being taught almost
130 exclusively to non-engineering students, who often lack the foundational technical training in
131 mechanics and physics required for an in-depth development of the subject (Pastukhov et al.,
132 2020). Consequently, academic staff teaching these disciplines must frequently adapt course
133 content to the background of students enrolled in Agricultural, Forest, or Food Science degree
134 programs. This pedagogical constraint risks diluting the scientific rigor and technological
135 innovation that characterizes Agricultural Engineering as a discipline, and enlarging the gap
136 between the requests that the professors receive from agri-food mechanical manufacturing
137 companies and the preparation given to the students. At the same time, students of Engineering
138 Degree programs are often unaware of the existence and potential of Agricultural Engineering,
139 due to its peripheral placement within the Italian university system and, above of all, the insulation
140 from the other engineering disciplines. This leads to a significant disconnect between the
141 competencies of graduates and the multidisciplinary demands of the labour market. Moreover,
142 the institutional separation between Agricultural and Engineering Departments limits opportunities
143 for cross-disciplinary collaboration, joint research initiatives, and co-supervised degree programs.
144 This is particularly detrimental in emerging fields such as agricultural robotics, smart farming, and
145 automation in food processing—areas that inherently require synergies among agronomists,
146 mechanical engineers, and data scientists (Fountas et al., 2015). The result of this insulation and

147 complete lack of visibility of Agricultural Engineering sector in Italy has resulted, for example, in
148 two courses in engineering showing the words “*Agricultural Engineering*” in their title (MSc in
149 Agritech Engineering at PoliTO, MSc in Agricultural Engineering at PoliMI) but without the direct
150 participation of any of the professors belonging to AGRI-04/B – “*Meccanica Agraria*”. Both those
151 courses are strangely positioned within the Master’s degree class LM-26 (“*Safety Engineering*”,
152 according to the Italian classification of university courses), implicitly demonstrating a degree of
153 indecision in the positioning of that MSc courses within the engineering disciplines, which clearly
154 do not include now Agricultural Engineering, being it currently positioned within the Area 07
155 “*Agricultural and Veterinary Sciences*”. Furthermore, there are some subjects belonging to the
156 AGRI-04/B sector (spec. related to Food Machinery/Equipment) in the study-plan of the BSc and
157 MSc course belonging to the degree class “L-26” and “LM-70” (“*Food Sciences and*
158 “*Technologies*”), but not in other MSc courses proposed within the Italian engineering schools, e.g.
159 in “*Engineering for the food industry*” (at the University of Parma), “*Engineering of Food*
160 “*Processes*” (at the University of Naples), “*Food Engineering*” (at the University of Salerno and
161 at Polimi), “*Food Industry Engineering*” (at the University of Padova), “*Food Engineering*” (at
162 University of Calabria), or in the curriculum “*Management of food production*” for the MSc in
163 “*Management Engineering*” (at University Tor Vergata).

164 Apart from the complete exclusion of the AGRI-04/B sector from all these degree courses, within
165 which this sector could have given for sure a contribution beside the other sectors already present
166 there, the problem at institutional level stems from some decrees approved by the Italian Ministry
167 of University and Scientific Research regarding the list of the Scientific-Disciplinary Sectors
168 (SSDs) involved in the “*Attività formative caratterizzanti*” (emg. “*Characterising learning*
169 “*activities*”) (Ministero dell’Università e della Ricerca Scientifica, 2024a, 2024b). In those decrees
170 of the AGRI-04/B sector is never mentioned outside of the BSc and MSc courses related to the
171 Agrifood.

172 Paradoxically, this academic misalignment persists de-spite strong and growing interest from
173 private companies in the agri-tech, food machinery, and forestry equipment sectors, which are
174 increasingly seeking engineers with hybrid expertise in mechanical systems and biological
175 processes. Moreover, in some countries, where Agricultural Engineering is a degree course
176 placed within the university faculties of agriculture, a recognized identity crisis of the figure of
177 Agricultural Engineer is occurring, as it is not recognised as a “*real engineer*” (Ajwang, 2017).
178 Therefore, other countries have embraced the interdisciplinary nature of the field through
179 dedicated degree programs (in “*Biosystems Engineering*”, “*Agro-industrial Engineering*”, or
180 “*Precision Agriculture Engineering*”), typically offered within Engineering faculties and supported
181 by integrated research platforms (EduRank, 2025).

182

183 **1.2 Need for multidisciplinary initiatives to promote Agricultural Engineering**

184

185 Given the institutional and didactic challenges outlined above—particularly the marginal
186 placement of Agricultural Engineering within non-engineering faculties and the resulting
187 fragmentation of expertise—there is a pressing need to promote multi-disciplinary initiatives
188 capable of bridging these structural divides. As highlighted, Agricultural and Agroforestry
189 Engineering in Italy are currently taught predominantly to students from agronomic or food science
190 backgrounds, limiting both the technical depth of instruction and the discipline’s integration into
191 broader engineering and technological ecosystems. This isolation stands in stark contrast to the
192 inherently interdisciplinary nature of the field, which demands the convergence of mechanical
193 design, control systems, environmental engineering, and biological sciences to address
194 contemporary challenges such as precision agriculture, digital farming, and sustainable agro-
195 industrial processing (Cathcart et al., 2005; Fountas et al., 2015; Opara, 2004).

196 Internationally, countries such as the United States (Master of Engineering in Digital Agriculture
197 and Master of Science in Agricultural and Biological Engineering, University of Illinois Urbana-
198 Champaign – The Grainger College of Engineering, MSc in Agricultural Engineering and Ph.D. in
199 Biological and Agricultural Engineering, University of Georgia, College of Engineering), France

200 (Master of Science and Engineering in Smart Farming and Sustainable Agriculture, Junia
201 Graduate School of Engineering), and the Netherlands (MSc in Crop Biotechnology and
202 Engineering, Maastricht University, Faculty of Science and Engineering) have successfully
203 institutionalized Agricultural Engineering within their Schools of Engineering, supported by cross-
204 departmental centres and multidisciplinary degree pro-grams in “*Biosystems Engineering*” or
205 “*Agro-industrial Engineering*” (Educations.com, 2025). These models demonstrate the benefits of
206 structurally embedding collaboration across disciplines and training profiles, thereby enhancing
207 the scientific visibility and industrial relevance of the field.

208 In Italy, overcoming the historical confinement of the sector AGRI-04/B – “*Meccanica Agraria*”
209 within Agricultural departments will require systemic reforms revising current curricula to include
210 cross-disciplinary modules, and hence national strategic investment in joint MSc and PhD
211 programs, shared research infrastructures, and coordinated efforts between Departments of
212 Engineering and Agricultural Sciences. Such efforts are essential to enhance the visibility,
213 scientific quality, and societal impact of the discipline and to align higher education with the
214 innovation needs of Italy’s agri-food and forestry sectors, particularly in the framework of the
215 National Recovery and Resilience Plan (PNRR), the Common Agricultural Policy (CAP), and
216 Horizon Europe. Therefore, these multidisciplinary initiatives are essential not only to strengthen
217 the academic identity of Agricultural Engineering, but also to meet the growing demand from
218 private sectors for hybrid professionals capable of operating across technical, environmental, and
219 biological domains. Ultimately, fostering such integration will enhance Italy’s capacity to contribute
220 to the agroecological and digital transitions envisioned in national and European innovation
221 agendas.

222 223 **1.3 The Role of the Contamination Lab in Supporting Multidisciplinary Integration and** 224 **Innovation in Agricultural Engineering**

225
226 In light of the structural fragmentation and disciplinary isolation described above, the
227 “*Contamination Lab*” (C-Lab) model can offer a promising, scalable solution to foster
228 multidisciplinary, didactic innovation, and university–industry collaboration in Agricultural and
229 Agroforestry Engineering. A Contamination Lab is an educational and innovation-oriented
230 platform that brings together students from different academic disciplines—e.g. engineering,
231 agronomy, economics, design, and computer science—to collaboratively address real-world
232 challenges posed by private companies, public administrations, and civil society organizations
233 (Fig. 2). These challenges are tackled through “project-based, team-oriented, and time-
234 constrained activities” that simulate professional innovation environments, with a strong focus on
235 prototyping, entrepreneurial thinking, and co-design processes (Governo Italiano, 2016; Graham,
236 2018; Ministero dell’Istruzione dell’Università e della Ricerca (MIUR), 2016; Proença, 2025;
237 Secundo et al., 2020). Activities within a Contamination Lab typically include intensive innovation
238 bootcamps, hackathons, design thinking sessions, and collaborative workshops focused on
239 generating viable solutions—ranging from conceptual prototypes to pre-commercial
240 demonstrators. These are often supported by mentors from both academia and industry and are
241 structured around iterative design methodologies such as the Lean Start-up (Ries, 2011) or Agile
242 Development (Agile Alliance, 2025) paradigms. Importantly, C-Labs emphasize “learning-by-
243 doing”, but differ from traditional laboratory courses or internship programs by being explicitly
244 interdisciplinary, problem-driven, and mission-oriented. Unlike FabLabs, which, instead, focus
245 primarily on digital fabrication and technological prototyping, or Living Labs, which often involve
246 co-creation with end-users in open environments, Contamination Labs serve as “transdisciplinary
247 innovation ecosystems” embedded within academic institutions, directly tied to educational
248 objectives and third mission outcomes (Pallot et al., 2010; Proença, 2025).

249

Figure 2. The six “pillars” of a contamination lab.

The key characteristics of a Contamination Lab are:

- *Multidisciplinarity and "Contamination"*: the name "Contamination Lab" comes just from the idea of encouraging the "contamination" of ideas and skills among students/participants coming from different disciplines/having different backgrounds (engineering, economics, humanities, arts, etc.). The goal is to generate innovative solutions that arise from the meeting of diverse perspectives.
- *Entrepreneurial Training and Guidance*: CLabs offer experiential training programs, often extracurricular, aimed at developing entrepreneurial skills, problem-solving abilities, teamwork, and idea presentation skills. Innovative teaching models like Design Thinking and Business Modelling are utilized.
- *Development of Concrete Projects*: students, possibly organized into teams that are as much multidisciplinary as possible, work on concrete project ideas with the support of expert tutors and mentors (entrepreneurs, managers, academics); the objective is to transform these ideas into feasible or real prototypes or viable, scalable, and sustainable business models.
- *Networking and Connection with the Territory*: CLabs act as a bridge between the university and the external world, facilitating relationships with companies, startups, incubators, investors, and other local stakeholders; this allows students to expand their network and engage with market demands and local opportunities.
- *Physical and Virtual Spaces*: CLabs can be both physical spaces dedicated to coworking, collaboration, and prototyping, as well as virtual platforms for sharing ideas and resources.
- *Start-up Support*: many CLabs offer pre-incubation services and access to resources and tools to help teams transform their ideas into innovative start-ups.

In the context of Agricultural Engineering, the C-Lab format is particularly well-suited to bridge existing gaps between agronomic knowledge and technological innovation, as it enables students to address real problems in agri-food systems—such as sustainable mechanization, digital agriculture, post-harvest optimization, and forest biomass valorisation—through exposure to diverse perspectives and industry practices (Murphy & Obenaus-Emler, 2025). A permanent C-Lab structure, embedded within or across Agricultural and Engineering departments, would not only facilitate institutional collaboration but also serve as a platform for engaging local and national companies in co-innovation processes. This supports the university’s third mission, facilitating knowledge transfer and strengthening links with stakeholders from sectors including agri-tech, food processing, machinery manufacturing, and environmental management.

1.4 Italian Regulatory Framework and Funding for Contamination Labs

In Italy, Contamination Labs have been primarily promoted and regulated by the (Italian) Ministry

291 of Education, University and Research (MIUR), now (from 2022 on) the Ministry of University and
292 Research (MUR) (Ministero dell'Università e della Ricerca, 2020). The main legislative references
293 and initiatives that have driven the establishment and development of CLabs are:

- 294 • Ministerial Decree No. 436 of March 13, 2013: this was one of the first acts to allocate funds
295 (€1 million) for the creation of Contamination Labs within universities; initially, the pilot project
296 involved only some regions of Southern Italy (Campania, Puglia, Calabria, and Sicily)
297 (PONREC, 2011).
- 298 • Guidelines on Contamination Labs (2016): The MUR published detailed guidelines for the
299 creation and development of CLabs. These guidelines define the objectives, methodologies,
300 desirable characteristics, and aims of Contamination Labs, emphasizing the importance of
301 multidisciplinary, entrepreneurial orientation, networking, and sustainability (Ministero
302 dell'Istruzione dell'Università e della Ricerca (MIUR), 2016).
- 303 • Ministerial Decree No. 3158 of November 29, 2016 (Public notice for the submission of
304 projects to support the creation and development of Contamination Labs); this decree
305 launched a call for specific projects, with the aim of supporting the creation and development
306 of CLabs and the establishment of a national CLab Network.
- 307 • Ministerial Decree of June 15, 2017, No. 1513 (Approval of rankings and implementation
308 guidelines for projects for the creation and development of Contamination Labs and the CLab
309 Network); this decree approved the rankings of projects funded following the 2016 call and
310 defined the implementation guidelines, establishing the management, execution, obligations,
311 and reporting procedures for universities admitted to funding. (Ministero dell'Istruzione e del
312 Merito, 2017); the funds came from the Development and Cohesion Fund (FSC), as part of
313 the National Research Program 2015-2020, in continuity with actions initiated in the previous
314 programming (PAC Ricerca).

315
316 These legislative acts provided the regulatory framework for Italian universities that wished to
317 establish a Contamination Lab, often including specific funding and the possibility of recognizing
318 university credits (CFU) for participating students.

319
320 The situation of Contamination Labs in Italy is still active and evolving, though with some specific
321 characteristics compared to their initial launch years. They continue to receive funding, but
322 through different channels:

- 323 1. PNRR (National Recovery and Resilience Plan): this is the most significant and recent funding
324 source for many CLabs and similar initiatives (Governo Italiano, 2021); under Mission 4
325 "Education and Research" and its components, the PNRR is allocating substantial resources
326 to strengthen the innovation ecosystem, applied research, and technology transfer; many
327 CLabs or initiatives that adopt their philosophy (such as the "Innovation Laboratories" or the
328 "Innovators Community Labs" in some universities) are integrated into larger PNRR-funded
329 projects, often within Innovation Eco-systems like iNEST for Northeast Italy, which includes
330 the University of Udine's CLab (Consorzio iNEST, 2025) or other national centres. This
331 ensures continuity of funding and greater integration with national development strategies.
- 332 2. European Structural Funds (ERDF, ESF); European structural funds, programmed at regional
333 or national levels, also continue to support innovation, research, and skills development
334 projects, in which CLabs or similar models can be included; for example, the "Digital
335 Contamination Lab 2025" by Lazio Innova is supported by the PR FESR Lazio 2021-2027
336 (Lazio Innova, 2025).
- 337 3. Self-funding and Local Collaborations; many universities, after receiving initial funding from
338 MUR (such as from the 2016-2017 call), have developed greater autonomy in managing and
339 raising resources. This occurs through:
 - 340 ○ Involvement of Private Companies; businesses actively participate in CLabs by
341 proposing challenges, providing mentors, or offering sponsor-ships, recognizing the
342 value of training and access to young talents and innovative ideas.
 - 343 ○ University Funds; universities themselves allocate part of their budgets to these

344 initiatives, as they are considered strategic for their "third mission" (knowledge
345 transfer and interaction with society).
346 ○ Regional or Local Calls; there are often specific regional or chamber of commerce
347 calls that support youth entrepreneurship and innovation.
348

349 As a consequence, the key aspects of the current situation can be delineated as follows:

- 350 • *Widespread Adoption*; most large Italian universities, and many medium-sized ones, now
351 have their own Contamination Lab or an equivalent initiative (often rebranded, such as the
352 Innovators Community Lab in Trieste (Università degli Studi di Trieste, 2025)), testifying to
353 the model's validity.
- 354 • *Specialization*; while initially CLabs had a more general scope, today there is a tendency to
355 specialize in strategic sectors (e.g., agro-forestry, digital, health, energy, tourism), often in line
356 with territorial vocations and funding priorities (like the PNRR).
- 357 • *Ecosystem Integration*; CLabs are increasingly seen as fundamental nodes of a broader
358 innovation ecosystem, which includes incubators, accelerators, science and technology
359 parks, and startups.
- 360 • *Academic Recognition*: Many CLabs still offer the students university ECTS credits (European
361 Commission: Directorate-General for Education, Youth, Sport and Culture, 2015), in Italy
362 referred to as "CFU", integrating the extracurricular training pathway with the traditional
363 academic curriculum.

364 **1.5 Other examples of Contamination Labs in Italy/world; characteristics and** 365 **differences with the current case** 366

367
368 Several Italian universities have adopted and adapted the C-Lab model (Fig. 3; Tab. 1). It is
369 important to note that, despite a ministerial imprint, each university retains the freedom to adapt
370 its Contamination Lab to its specific characteristics and local context, while maintaining the core
371 principles of "contamination" and entrepreneurial orientation. Among the most consolidated, there
372 are: the "Contamination Lab Cagliari", one of the earliest and most influential, with strong links to
373 ICT and entrepreneurship (Università degli Studi di Cagliari, 2025a); the "Contamination Lab San
374 Giovanni a Teduccio" at the University of Naples Federico II (Università degli Studi di Napoli
375 "Federico II," 2015), focusing on smart cities, sustainability, and agri-food technologies (Università
376 degli Studi di Napoli "Parthenope," 2022); and the "C-Lab Sapienza" (Sapienza Università di
377 Roma, 2021, 2026), which links engineering, architecture, and social sciences through open
378 innovation processes. These labs differ in their governance models, thematic focus, and degree
379 of integration into formal curricula.

380 In general, Italian Contamination Labs range from ICT- and start-up-oriented (Cagliari, Bologna,
381 Pisa) to sector-specialized hubs, such as the CLab of Faenza, having an agriculture/food focus
382 (EmiliaRomagnaStartup, 2025). Some (e.g., Pisa) awards academic credits and formal
383 integration (Università degli Studi di Pisa, 2025).
384

Figure 3. Universities belonging to the Italian CLAB network (figure taken from (CLab@Salento, 2026)).

Table 1. Examples of Contamination Labs in Italy & Abroad (Università degli Studi di Cagliari, 2025b)

Lab	Location	Key Features / Focus	Notes
C-Lab Cagliari	University of Cagliari, Italy	ICT, entrepreneurship, startup acceleration; follows projects beyond launch	One of the earliest Italian C-Labs
C-Lab Pisa	University of Pisa, Italy	Graduate/PhD level; design thinking, business modelling	Offers PhD+ and CyB+ programs with academic credits
C-Lab Naples	University of Napoli, Italy	Smart cities, sustainability, agri-food tech	Collaborates with local companies and public bodies
C-Lab Faenza	Faenza (Ravenna), Italy	Open space + digital; idea-stage entrepreneurship	Agriculture and food sector focus
d.school Stanford	Stanford University, USA	Design thinking, innovation, cross-faculty education	Emphasis on entrepreneurial mindset and systemic design
Design Factory	Aalto University & global, Finland	Product development, multidisciplinary innovation	Part of a global engineering-design innovation network
EPFL Changemakers	EPFL, Switzerland	Entrepreneurial, social & tech innovation	Living Lab hybrid focused on sustainability

394 Contamination Labs have generated several significant experiences since their inception,
 395 contributing substantially to promoting entrepreneurship and innovation in the university context.
 396 While it's challenging to compile an exhaustive ranking of the "most relevant," as success can be
 397 measured in various ways (number of start-ups generated, territorial impact, project quality, etc.),
 398 we can identify some experiences that have stood out for their visibility, innovation, or impact on
 399

400 the territory:

- 401 1. CLab Torino (Politecnico di Torino and University of Turin) (Fiore et al., 2019; Politecnico di
402 Torino, Università di Torino, 2026):
 - 403 ○ Relevance: It was the first inter-university Contamination Lab in Italy, resulting from
404 the collaboration between two major universities in a city with a strong industrial and
405 innovative vocation.
 - 406 ○ Impact: It offered a unique environment for students and PhD candidates from diverse
407 disciplines, promoting the experimentation of new learning models and the
408 development of projects with entrepreneurial and social aims, closely linked to the
409 challenges of the Turin area.
- 410 2. Contamination Lab of the University of Pisa:
 - 411 ○ Relevance: The Pisa CLab is an example of continuity and adaptation, having evolved
412 its focus on spreading entrepreneurial education and promoting a culture of innovation
413 with a strong emphasis on sustainability as a key element of value creation.
 - 414 ○ International Visibility: Recently, Professor A. Cavicchi, scientific director of the Pisa
415 CLab, was invited by the European Commission to present the "case of the Pisa
416 Contamination Lab" at an international event on entrepreneurship ("Entrepreneurial
417 Skills and Competences Throughout Life"), demonstrating its European recognition.
 - 418 ○ Collaborations: It organized workshops in collaboration with European alliances (such
419 as the "Start For Future Alliance") to support research teams and start-ups, facilitating
420 the creation of innovative enterprises.
- 421 3. Contamination Lab Trento (University of Trento and HIT - Hub Innovazione Trentino)
422 (Università degli Studi di Trento, 2026):
 - 423 ○ Relevance: It has distinguished itself by its strong integration with the highly
424 developed Trentino innovation ecosystem. The partnership with HIT has enabled the
425 creation of an environment where innovation and entrepreneurial culture are taught
426 both to complete students' traditional education and to promote new successful
427 activities based on real cases and industrial needs.
 - 428 ○ Internationalization: It has a strong focus on international "contamination," allowing
429 participants to work with international teams and mentors.
- 430 4. Digital Contamination Lab (Lazio Innova in collaboration with several Lazio universities):
 - 431 ○ Relevance: While not strictly university-led in its organization like others, Lazio
432 Innova's "Digital Contamination Lab" is a significant example of how the CLab
433 methodology has been adopted by regional development agencies, in collaboration
434 with multiple universities (e.g., University of Tuscia, Cassino, Sapienza).
 - 435 ○ Strategic Sectors: It focuses on high-potential sectors such as Environment and
436 Energy, Digital, Culture and Tourism, Health and Social Well-being, and has awarded
437 innovative projects with a concrete impact on the Lazio territory.
- 438 5. Contamination Lab of the University of Padua (CLab Unipd) (Università degli Studi di Padova,
439 2026b, 2026a):
 - 440 ○ Relevance: It has a consolidated history and has seen the participation of important
441 industrial entities like Stevanato Group and Irinox, demonstrating how CLabs can be
442 fertile ground for innovative relationships between academia and industry, leading to
443 the birth of successful entrepreneurial initiatives. It has a strong focus on spreading
444 entrepreneurial culture and developing projects with market appeal.

445
446 Other universities in Italy in which a Contamination Lab took place are: University of Basilicata
447 (Università degli Studi della Basilicata, 2026), University of Brescia (Università degli Studi di
448 Brescia, 2026), University Carlo Cattaneo (Università Carlo Cattaneo – LIUC, 2026), University
449 of Catania (Università degli Studi di Catania, 2026), University of Genova (Università degli Studi
450 di Genova, 2026), Online University Mercatorum (Università Telematica Universitas Mercatorum,
451 2026), University of Modena and Reggio Emilia, (Università degli Studi di Modena e Reggio
452 Emilia, 2026), University of Molise (Università del Molise, 2026), University of Palermo (Università

453 degli Studi di Palermo, 2026), Polytechnical University of Marche (Università Politecnica delle
454 Marche, 2018), University of Salento (CLab@Salento, 2026), University of Teramo (Università
455 degli Studi di Teramo, 2025), University of Venezia (Università Ca' Foscari, 2026), University of
456 Verona (Università degli Studi di Verona, 2026).

457

458 These experiences demonstrate how Contamination Labs have become a pillar for innovation in
459 Italian universities, not only by training new generations of entrepreneurs but also by acting as
460 catalysts for technology transfer and value creation in their respective territories.

461 Internationally, initiatives akin to the C-Lab format include the “Design Factory Global Network”
462 (originated at Aalto University, Finland), the “d.school at Stanford University” (Hasso Plattner
463 Institute of Design at Stanford University, 2025), and the “EPFL Changemakers” program in
464 Switzerland (École Polytechnique Fédérale de Lausanne - APLF, 2023) —each promoting cross-
465 disciplinary, project-based innovation embedded within higher education (Jussila et al., 2020),
466 with a systemic impact—principles that align well with Africa/ Agricultural Engineering
467 applications. Many labs currently lean towards general innovation or ICT; a domain-specific lab
468 in Agricultural and Biosystems Engineering—embedded in agronomy + engineering faculties and
469 focused on agri-tech, mechanization, post-harvest processing, forest systems—would be a
470 strategic innovation, combining lessons from both national and international models.

471

472

2. Methods

473

2.1 The University of Udine's Contamination Lab: A Different Approach to Raising 475 Awareness of Agricultural Engineering and Engage Companies

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477 The Agroforestry Engineering C-Lab of the University of Udine (Università degli Studi di Udine,
478 2025) has a strong focus on applied research and the resolution of specific problems proposed
479 by companies, just as the sector to which it is referred. This perspective, while not excluding
480 entrepreneurship as a potential ultimate outcome (e.g. possible creation of start-ups after this
481 experience), emphasizes co-creation of solutions and technology transfer more strongly. We can
482 say that this C-Lab stands out for its strong emphasis on "Corporate Problem Solving and
483 Collaborative Research" as the main driver of innovation, while still retaining elements that can
484 lead to entrepreneurship. Furthermore, one of the crucial points in pursuing “third mission”
485 activities by university professors is always to come in contact with potentially interested
486 companies. The former, indeed, does not have adequate resources to actively carry out real and
487 effective scouting or advertising activities, as it is also (rightly) engaged in other areas related to
488 teaching and basic research. (i.e., the first and second missions) The latter, on the other hand,
489 may not be aware of all the expertise and people they could find at the university and end up
490 contacting only those they already know. Although mainly aimed at students, a C-Lab focused on
491 Agroforestry Engineering is also an excellent opportunity to bring these two subjects together.
492 Indeed, it filters companies to only those that are genuinely interested in the sector (or that already
493 define themselves as part of it) and shifts the burden of engagement onto them through an
494 advertising campaign on institutional channels (therefore having a lower effort than one aimed at
495 a specific target).

496 More into detail, the Agroforestry Engineering C-Lab of the University of Udine unfolded through
497 the following steps:

498 1. Collection of adhesions from companies and request for a definition of challenges by them:
499 companies presented real problems, problematic points, or opportunities for improvement/
500 innovation that required a research and development approach; this was at the heart of the
501 "research collaboration"; specifically, in the 2025 edition, solutions were requested for these
502 themes (see following paragraphs for a higher detail):

503

- Optimization of water resource management in agriculture.

504

- Development of smart sensors for crop monitoring.

- 505 • Solutions for phytoremediation.
- 506 • Market analysis of liquid food mixing products.
- 507 2. Formation of multidisciplinary teams; participating students (mainly from engineering,
- 508 computer science, agricultural sciences) were organized into teams, trying to enhance
- 509 multidisciplinary, as it is crucial for tackling complex problems from various angles.
- 510 3. Problem analysis and understanding phase; the teams applied methodologies like Design
- 511 Thinking, hence, they dedicated time to:
 - 512 • thoroughly understanding the needs and perspectives of the company and the end-
 - 513 users of the problem (empathy);
 - 514 • clearly outlining the problem to be solved (Statement Definition);
 - 515 • generating a wide range of ideas for solutions (Ideation);
- 516 4. Solution development and prototyping phase; the teams worked on developing concepts,
- 517 prototypes (even just conceptual, virtual or low-fidelity), and/or feasibility studies for the
- 518 proposed solutions; the focus was on the technical validity and innovation of the solution to
- 519 the corporate problem rather than on the "business model"
- 520 5. Specialized mentoring; participants received support from:
 - 521 • University professors and researchers, specifically for the scientific and technical
 - 522 validity of the solutions;
 - 523 • Company experts, to ensure the applicability and relevance of the solutions in the
 - 524 industrial context.
 - 525 • Innovation experts, to guide the problem-solving process.
- 526 6. Presentation and feedback: at the end of the C-Lab, the teams presented their solutions to
- 527 the proposing companies and a jury of experts. Feedback was crucial for refining ideas and
- 528 evaluating their future applicability.
- 529 7. Analytical evaluation of proposals, ranking of groups and award ceremony.

530

531 What distinguishes it and why it is an effective model:

- 532 • *Strengthening the third mission*: this approach maximally emphasizes the university's "third
- 533 mission": technology transfer and territorial impact. It's not just about producing knowledge,
- 534 but directly applying it to solve concrete problems for businesses.
- 535 • *Developing highly demanded skills*: students acquire not only entrepreneurial skills but also
- 536 applied research, incremental/disruptive innovation for industry, collaborative problem-
- 537 solving, and project management with external stakeholders. These are highly sought-after
- 538 skills in the job market, both in established corporate settings and in start-ups.
- 539 • *Pipeline for Corporate Innovation*: For companies, participation means gaining access to new
- 540 ideas, fresh talent, and an innovative approach to solving problems that they might not be
- 541 able to address internally with the same speed or perspective. It could lead to the adoption of
- 542 new technologies or the initiation of joint internal R&D projects.
- 543 • *Indirect Entrepreneurial Potential*: Even if the primary orientation is not immediate start-up
- 544 creation, the most promising solutions could still evolve into:
 - 545 • Broader joint research projects.
 - 546 • Hiring of participants by the companies.
 - 547 • Spin-offs or start-ups if the solution has sufficient market potential to justify an
 - 548 independent entrepreneurial path (e.g., the developed solution can be a
 - 549 product/service saleable to other companies).
- 550 • Role of PNRR and iNEST: Being part of the PNRR and iNEST context means that this CLab
- 551 is part of a broader strategy for strengthening innovation and competitiveness in Northeast
- 552 Italy, with a clear mandate to facilitate collaboration between research and industry.

553

554 Ultimately, the Udine CLab, with this specific focus, not only distinguishes itself by a more applied

555 collaborative research approach but also represents a virtuous model of how the university can

556 become a strategic partner for corporate innovation, generating mutual value and training

557 professionals with highly specialized and in-demand skills.

558

559 **2.2 Communication media that enabled recruitment**

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561 The selection of participating students was conducted through a multichannel communication
562 campaign:

563 • Social Channels: advertising on the University's profiles on the main social networks
564 (Facebook, Instagram, LinkedIn).

565 • Direct Communication: sending an email to all the university students (15269 students at that
566 time).

567 • Institutional Media: dissemination of announcements on the main university media and
568 noticeboards.

569 • Posters/Flyers: posters displayed in the main university locations (spec. access to classroom
570 buildings and study rooms).

571

572 The graphics for all press releases/posts/flyers were entrusted to a professional graphic design
573 studio and featured an image that captured the viewer's attention while also evoking the idea of
574 a technological approach to agri-environmental issues. (Fig.4) It functions as a visual manifesto
575 for the C-Lab in Agroforestry Engineering. Indeed, the anthropomorphic figure composed of
576 vegetal elements symbolizes the integration of humans within agro-ecosystems, conveying a
577 systemic and regenerative vision of engineering that overcomes the traditional nature–technology
578 dichotomy. The presence of drones represents advanced digital technologies—such as precision
579 agriculture and forestry—as enabling, non-invasive tools that enhance ecosystem understanding
580 rather than dominate it. The figure's reflective posture communicates responsibility, care, and
581 ethical agency, highlighting the role of the agroforestry engineer as a conscious manager of
582 complex socio-ecological systems. The natural, desaturated color palette reinforces ideas of
583 balance, sustainability, and a desirable technological future. Overall, the image visually
584 encapsulates the concept of disciplinary contamination by merging ecology, engineering, and
585 innovation into a coherent narrative aligned with contemporary agroforestry education.

586

587

588 **Figure 4.** Distinctive image proposed for C-lab Udine (Università degli Studi di
589 Udine, 2025).

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591 A subsequent survey revealed that the majority of participants enrolled after receiving the direct
592 email. A small number participated due to word-of-mouth, and only one student responded to the
593 social network advertising. No participants reported enrolling after seeing the posters displayed
594 on campus.

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2.3 Participating companies and proposed challenges

The Contamination Lab, named "*Agroforestry Engineering C-Lab*", took place from May 2 to May 16, 2025. Four different companies participated, proposing four distinct research topics, collected in Tab. 2.

Table 2. Research topics proposed by the four involved companies.

Title	Description
Soil Moisture Mapping	This research sought methods and tools to map soil moisture in agricultural plots at various depths (from the surface down to 50-60 cm) with a spatial resolution of 2-5 square meters. The aim was to spatialize predictive models for diseases or crop water status, which are typically based on soil moisture measurements from point sensors installed in the field, as well as other climatic or canopy data provided by a localized weather station. The request was to delve deeper into specific aspects of the proposed systems, such as: <ul style="list-style-type: none">• Measurement reliability, depending on the physical mechanism involved.• Applicability limits.• Costs.• Ease of use for a farmer.
Phytoremediation and Vermicomposting	This research involved designing a compact and modular system for managing agro-food industry waste sludge through vermicomposting of the solid part and phytoremediation of the liquid part.
Thermo-Chemical and Mechanical Performance within Tanks and Mixers for the Food Industry	This research focused on the processes related to thermo-chemical and mechanical transformations occurring within tanks for liquid foodstuffs (wine, beer, tea, kombucha, fruit juices, oils and fats, vegetable pulps, beverages in general, distillates, liqueurs, concentrates, sugary solutions, brines, emulsions, etc.). The goal was to understand the dynamics of component and temperature homogenization, element dissolution, and optimal fluid agitation as container geometry and mixing system characteristics vary, ultimately identifying the salient features and performance of agitation systems.
The Future of Irrigation for Agricultural Crops	Agricultural crop irrigation faces significant challenges. Future trends indicate that more precise control, improved monitoring, and reduced water consumption will be fundamental. The objective of this project was to analyse current and future irrigation requirements and develop innovative solutions.

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Each company provided a corporate tutor whose role was to present the participants the proposed research topic and explain them the expected results from the company's perspective. Eighteen students from 13 different degree programs participated in finding solutions to these research topics. They were instructed to split into four groups of 4-5 students, i.e. one group for each participating company, after the process described hereinafter. The initial phase began with a Team Building session where the students, after listening to the presentations about each topic, were tasked with self-organizing and dividing themselves into

612 groups; the goal was to create groups that were as balanced as possible in terms of skills,
 613 experience, and interest in the chosen topic, specifically considering the following parameters:

- 614 • Degree program of origin.
- 615 • Year and type of attended course.
- 616 • Personal preferences for a research topic.

617
 618 The students successfully formed their groups independently in about half an hour, however
 619 following the organizers' suggestions. The primary goal of the academic tutors was to ensure the
 620 formation of multidisciplinary and balanced groups, paying particular attention to harmonizing the
 621 distribution of skills/academic paths and the year of enrolment at the University. Each group was
 622 then assigned a corporate tutor, based on the chosen topic, and an academic tutor. The groups
 623 then began their research work, which they were to complete over two weeks, consulting with
 624 both their corporate and academic tutors.

625
 626 **2.4 Proposed seminars**

627
 628 Within the CLab, some seminars were also held to provide students with additional
 629 tools/approaches to best develop their research topics. Specifically, the following seminars were
 630 offered:

- 631 • *“Foresight Lab to Explore Tomorrow”*, Prof. C. Battistella & Dr. Eng. G. Attanasio, UniUD;
- 632 • *“Practical Creativity Workshop for Innovation”*, Prof. C. Battistella & Dr. Eng. G. Attanasio,
 633 UniUD;
- 634 • *“From Wool, Flowers are Born”*, Dr. C. Spigarelli, freelance
- 635 • *“Effective Management of Complex Projects”*, Prof. C. Battistella & Dr. Eng. G. Attanasio,
 636 UniUD;
- 637 • *“From Idea to Enterprise”*, Dr. P.P. Ganis – Vitesy.

638
 639 At the end of the two weeks, the groups prepared a summary document of their results, created
 640 a three-minute pitch to summarize their findings, and presented their research directly to a mixed
 641 jury equally composed of university professors and company professionals, who evaluated the
 642 work of the individual groups. The evaluation was conducted considering the following criteria
 643 (Tab. 3), each of them was awarded with a score spanning from 1 (*“non-sufficient”*) to 5
 644 (*“excellent”*):

645
 646 **Table 3.** Evaluation criteria.
 647

Criterion	Evaluation Description
1. Project Presentation	Clarity of exposition, logical structure of the presentation, effective use of visual or multimedia aids, ability to attract and maintain audience attention.
2. Communication Skills	Language proficiency, appropriate use of technical-scientific vocabulary, coherence and fluidity in a presentation, ability to respond effectively to any questions or observations.
3. Understanding of Proposed Research Topic	Demonstration of in-depth understanding of the assigned topic, contextualization of the problem, ability to synthesize sources and underlying needs.

4. Evaluation of Proposed Solution Originality and innovativeness of the idea, technical feasibility, sustainability (environmental, economic, social), consistency with the topic's objectives.

5. Ability to Work in a Group Quality of collaboration among team members, balanced distribution of tasks, integration of individual contributions into a unified project. Ability to address and resolve conflicts or operational difficulties.

648

649 During and in the follow-up of the laboratory, questionnaires were administered to both
650 participants and corporate tutors to evaluate the experience, which we report in the analysis
651 section.

652

653 **2.5 Participating students**

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655 16 of the 17 participants were students from the University of Udine, while only one student came
656 from another Italian institution. The students showed remarkable academic diversity, coming from
657 13 different Italian degree programs (Tab. 4). The breakdown by Department of reference for their
658 degree programs was as follows:

- 659 • 8 students from the Department of Agri-Food, Environmental and Animal Sciences (DI4A)
660 of UniUD (degree programs broadly related to Agriculture, Food, Environment);
- 661 • 3 students from the Department of Mathematics, Computer Science and Physics (DMIF)
662 of UniUD (degrees broadly related to Computer Science and Informatics);
- 663 • 3 students from the Polytechnic Department of Engineering and Architecture (DPIA) of
664 UniUD (degree programs broadly related to Engineering);
- 665 • 3 students from other departments/universities.

666

667 Regarding the level of study (Fig. 5), the majority (11) came from Bachelor's degree programs,
668 but there were also students enrolled in Master's degree programs (5), and one student who was
669 pursuing a Ph.D. program.

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Figure 5. Distribution of Students by University Level of enrolment.

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Table 4. Teams Composition: Detail of students' degree programs (including also the degree classes (Ministero dell'Università e della Ricerca Scientifica, 2024a, 2024b)) and research topics.

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Research topic / Team topic	St. ID	Official Course Denomination	Deg. Class
	1	Cultural Mediation	L-12

Thermo-Chemical and Mechanical Performance within Tanks and Mixers for the Food Industry	2	Viticulture and Oenology	L-25
	3	Viticulture and Oenology	L-25
	4	Biotechnology	L-2
Soil Moisture Mapping	5	Viticulture and Oenology	PhD
	6	Internet of Things, Big Data, Machine Learning	L-31
	7	Computer Science / Informatics	L-31
	8	Mechanical Engineering	LM-33
Phytoremediation and Vermicomposting	9	Industrial Engineering for Sustainable Manufacturing	LM-31
	10	Food Science and Technology	LM-70
	11	Biotechnology	L-2
	12	Biotechnology	L-2
	13	Artificial Intelligence & Cybersecurity	LM-18
The Future of Irrigation for Agricultural Crops	14	Electronic Engineering	L-8
	15	Agricultural Sciences	L-25
	16	Public relations	L-20
	17	Territorial and Urban Planning	LM-48

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The distribution of average exam marks at the date of participation to the C-Lab (Fig. 6) suggests a high (spontaneous) selection standard for the Contamination Lab, evidenced by the dominant presence of students with high academic performance (peaks at 25 and 30 over 30) and the absence of marks below 21 upon 30, indicating a sample composed of highly motivated participants with a solid theoretical foundation.

Figure 6. Distribution of students based on the average mark of passed exams.

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The distribution by percentage of completed exams (Fig. 7) reveals a heterogeneous sample composition, characterized by two distinct prevailing groups. There is indeed a large segment at mid-course (50 % of completed exams), which guarantees energy and updated knowledge, and another significant group of senior students (90 % of completed exams), which contributes maturity and result-orientation.

Figure 7. Distribution of students based on the percentage of completed exams.

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The distribution by enrolment year (Fig. 8) reveals a strong presence of recently enrolled students (2024, i.e. students with only one year of university study), ensuring fresh perspectives within the Contamination Lab, complemented by a balanced mix of students from various other academic cohorts (e.g., 2018, 2020, and 2022), which guarantees a crucial combination of academic experience and novelty.

Figure 8. Distribution of students by university enrolment year.

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The analysis by completed years of university (Fig. 9) reveals a strongly bimodal and polarized composition, with dominant groups at the 1st year and the 5th year, ensuring maximum intergenerational contamination between students with fresh perspectives and those with high academic maturity and deep theoretical knowledge.

Figure 9. Distribution of students by completed years of university.

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3. Results

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3.1 Feedback from companies on students' outcomes

Company tutors were asked to provide specific feedback, by completing a questionnaire, on three main areas:

- the research outcomes,
- the relationship established with the student group,
- the overall collaboration between the company and the University.

The data collected yielded the following results:

- Research Outcomes; all company tutors agreed that the groups failed to present ideas that were truly innovative or immediately interesting for concrete application; despite this, three out of four tutors expressed an overall positive evaluation of the work carried out by their research group; only one tutor gave a strongly negative assessment.
- Relationship with the Research Group; the relationship between the company tutors and their respective research groups was reported to be generally good; however, in the majority of cases, a lack of initiative in interaction on the part of the groups was highlighted; one tutor was particularly critical of their group, while another expressed great satisfaction with the established relationship.
- Company-University Collaboration; all company tutors expressed a very positive evaluation regarding the collaboration with the University and indicated their willingness to repeat the experience.

3.2 Feedback from participating students

Students were asked to provide feedback by completing a questionnaire. The evaluation specifically covered:

- The level of interest shown towards the assigned research topic.
- The quality of the relationship between the group and the company tutor.
- The internal dynamics and relationships among group members.
- A general assessment of the overall experience within the CLab.

The analysis of the questionnaires revealed the following results:

- Interest in the Topic; one group expressed a critical evaluation of the research topic, describing it as uninteresting because it focused on market research rather than the development of a product or service; all other participants stated they were satisfied with the assigned topic.
- Relationship with Company Tutor; only one group gave an unsatisfactory rating regarding the relationship with their company tutor; all other participants evaluated this relationship positively.
- Group Dynamics; a critical issue regarding the ability to work as a team was found in two out of four groups; in one case, the problem was attributed to the individual conduct of one member; in the other, to a lack of harmonious cooperation among participants.
- Overall CLab Assessment; almost all participants and all groups expressed a broadly positive opinion of the initiative promoted by the University and stated they would be willing to repeat the experience; only one participant expressed a critical view of the initiative, indicating they would not be willing to repeat it.

3.3 Feedback from academic tutor

The feedback received from academic tutors, the students and company tutors were all agreeing,

767 while providing further information.

768

769 Specifically, the following critical points emerged:

770 • In two groups, a lack of internal cohesion was observed, which negatively affected the final
771 outcome of the research work.

772 • In all groups, communication with the company tutor was insufficient, preventing an optimal
773 alignment between the group's work and the company's expectations.

774 • In one case, a lack of proactive attitude was also noted on the part of a participating company,
775 whose evaluation was found to be in disagreement with the final judgment expressed by the
776 jury.

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4. Discussion

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4.1 Academic Background and Performance Correlation of Participants

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782 The analysis of the participants' academic data revealed several interesting correlations with the
783 final project ranking, evidenced by the determination coefficients of the regression lines plotted
784 on the data.

785 The first graph presented here (Fig. 10) highlights a negative correlation between final ranking
786 and years of attendance demonstrating that the groups achieving the best final ranking are, on
787 average, those composed of students with the highest number of years of university attendance
788 (and, presumably, the widest and richest competencies).

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Figure 10. Average years of attendance of university courses vs final ranking

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793 The graph of Fig. 11 demonstrates a strong, positive, and apparently counter-intuitive correlation,
794 indicating that the Contamination Lab groups with the highest percentage of academic path
795 completion tend to achieve the worst final ranking. However, this piece of information should be
796 related to the previous figure, considering that the higher the number of attended academic years,
797 the higher the possibility for students not to have completed their academic grades.

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Figure 11 Completion of academic path vs final ranking.

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The graph of Fig. 12 reveals a strong negative correlation indicating that the Contamination Lab groups with the highest average mark of passed exams are the ones that unequivocally have achieved the best final ranking.

Figure 12. Average mark of passed exams vs. final ranking at the CLab.

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Summarizing the data, the groups that achieve the best final ranking are, on average, those composed of students with the highest average mark of passed exams (strong negative correlation) and the highest number of years of university attendance (negative correlation). This suggests that fundamental cognitive capacity and academic maturity—developed through both successful study performance and long-term exposure to the university environment—are critical success factors in the C-Lab. These attributes translate into greater discipline, better problem-solving skills, and superior ability to synthesize complex though different information, which are essential for addressing the corporate challenges.

A strong, positive, and, at the first sight, counter-intuitive correlation was also observed: the groups with the highest percentage of academic path completion tend to achieve the worst final ranking. This potential divergence between the skills valued in a conventional curriculum (focused on quick exam completion) and those required by the C-Lab (creative exploration, risk-taking, and open-ended innovation) warrants further investigation even if it can be explained at first instance considering that the higher possibility for students not to have completed their academic grades if their academic path is longer, as for students with more attended academic years. This is in accordance with the first result. However, it is essential to note that the validity and generalizability of this counter-intuitive correlation must be evaluated with caution, given the limited sample size of C-Lab participants, which may not guarantee sufficient statistical power and representativeness to exclude the risk of a sampling error.

831 **4.2 Why Companies Should Participate in a Contamination Lab (C-Lab) Instead of**
832 **Seeking Traditional Academic Consultancy**
833

834 Engaging in a Contamination Lab offers companies operating in the development of engineering
835 systems for agri-food, forestry, and environmental sectors a fundamentally different—and often
836 more strategic—form of collaboration with the university compared to simply requesting technical
837 advice or consultancy. While conventional university–industry interactions are typically vertical,
838 involving a direct and expert response to a narrowly defined technical problem, the C-Lab model
839 promotes horizontal co-creation, where innovation emerges from an open, multidisciplinary
840 dialogue between students, researchers, and company representatives.

841 In a C-Lab, companies propose real-world challenges not to be solved through a predefined
842 method, but to be explored creatively by interdisciplinary student teams using design thinking,
843 rapid prototyping, and agile innovation methodologies. This approach allows firms to tap into
844 cognitive diversity and uncover ideas that are not constrained by existing technical paradigms—
845 often producing unexpected, unconventional yet applicable solutions. In this regard, a C-Lab in
846 Agricultural Engineering provides an ideal environment for the application of advanced systemic
847 methodologies for functional analysis, problem-solving and creativity guidance, such as the TRIZ,
848 i.e. the 'Theory of Inventive Problem Solving' (Wikipedia, 2026), developed by Genrich Altshuller
849 and his colleagues since 1946 and formalized in 1984 (Altshuller, 1984).

850 Moreover, C-Labs serve as powerful platforms to promote corporate visibility and foster talent
851 scouting. By participating, companies position themselves as dynamic and innovation-oriented
852 actors within the academic ecosystem, gaining access, at the same time, to a pool of motivated
853 students who may become future collaborators, interns, or employees whose competencies and
854 attitudes are already tested in applied, team-based contexts. Unlike in traditional consultancy
855 relationships, the C-Lab enables ongoing, informal interaction between companies and students
856 throughout the challenge development process, creating deeper mutual understanding and long-
857 term recruitment opportunities.

858 Another key advantage lies in the risk–benefit profile of these initiatives: the participation in a C-
859 Lab is low-cost and low-risk for companies, but potentially high-reward, especially for SMEs and
860 start-ups lacking internal R&D capabilities. Companies are actively involved in defining challenge
861 briefs, mentoring, and evaluating project outcomes. Beyond immediate outputs, this engagement
862 is not limited to a passive sponsorship: it also fosters alignment with the university's third mission
863 by contributing to knowledge transfer, entrepreneurship, and innovation ecosystems, enhancing
864 the reputation of participating companies among emerging professionals and within the university
865 networks. Hence, it is possible to state that a Contamination Lab is not merely a support service—
866 it is a collaborative innovation environment where companies are active stakeholders in shaping
867 both educational and technological outcomes (Graham, 2018; Ministero dell'Istruzione
868 dell'Università e della Ricerca (MIUR), 2016).

869
870 **4.3 Strategic Advantages for a University in Hosting a Recurring Contamination Lab on**
871 **Agricultural Engineering**
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873 For universities that host both Engineering and Agricultural Sciences departments, establishing
874 and continuously supporting a Contamination Lab (C-Lab) dedicated to Agricultural Engineering
875 offers strategic, didactic, and institutional advantages that extend far beyond the timeframe of
876 individual editions. Agricultural Engineering, by its very nature, operates at the intersection of
877 technical and biological systems, addressing complex challenges in agri-food, forestry, and
878 environmental domains through an inherently multidisciplinary and a technical, application-
879 oriented approach (Fig. 13). As such, a recurring C-Lab focused on this field can enhance the
880 university's capacity to act as an integrated innovation hub—making, at the same time, the
881 Agricultural Engineering group (and subject) more visible both internally and externally. This
882 visibility is particularly valuable in positioning the university as a reference point for companies
883 developing machinery, automation or digital solutions for bio-based systems, offering them a clear

884 gateway to a coherent and well-coordinated academic interlocutor.
 885 Moreover, the Agricultural Engineering research group/subject, due to its hybrid nature and
 886 systems-level vision, is uniquely suited to coordinate and synthesize contributions from vertical
 887 research groups in both Engineering (e.g., control systems, materials, electronics) and
 888 Agricultural Sciences (e.g., agronomy, animal science, food technology). A C-Lab can become a
 889 catalyst for such interdisciplinary collaboration, reinforcing internal synergies and enabling the
 890 creation of truly transdisciplinary project teams. This bridging function—akin to the role played by
 891 Management Engineering between technical and economical disciplines—makes Agricultural
 892 Engineering a strategic driver of cross-sectoral innovation and policy-relevant research.
 893 From a governance and investment perspective, supporting a C-Lab in Agricultural Engineering
 894 also ensures high return on educational and institutional investment: the relevance of the field
 895 spans multiple sectors, including mechanization, food processing, forestry, water and soil
 896 management, and sustainability transitions. This breadth means that each iteration of the C-Lab
 897 contributes to multiple strategic priorities simultaneously—regional development, innovation
 898 ecosystems, green transition, and industrial partnerships. For these reasons, the continued
 899 investment in such a format not only strengthens the role of Agricultural Engineering within the
 900 university but also maximizes the institutional impact per unit of resource deployed, aligning
 901 perfectly with third-mission objectives and long-term research valorisation, in a win-win strategy.
 902

903
 904 **Figure 13.** Possible role of Agricultural Engineering in relation to the Domains of
 905 Application/Interest (bio- or mechanical systems) and the Areas of Influence (within
 906 or outside the university); within this matrix, “horizontal” relations (i.e. between cells
 907 in an horizontal direction in this matrix) are interlocutions, “vertical” relations are
 908 collaborations.
 909

910 5. Conclusions

911 5.1 Synthesis of Results and Model Validation

912 The results emerged from this case-study empirically confirm that the Contamination Lab (C-Lab)
 913 represents a necessary and scalable “hybrid response” to the difficult positioning of Agricultural
 914 Engineering in Italy. The marginalization of this sector has historically created a communication
 915 gap with engineering and technological disciplines and a lack of visibility toward companies
 916 manufacturing agri-tech, food machinery, and forestry equipment; the C-Lab has demonstrated
 917 its ability to bridge this gap by acting as a platform for institutional mediation. The validation of the
 918 model rests on three fundamental pillars:
 919

- 921 • *Effectiveness of the so-called “Technological Triad” (Agriculture, Engineering, Computer
 922 Science):* the platform facilitated a transdisciplinary collaboration that conventional
 923 departmental systems tend to inhibit. The success of the groups depended on the ability to
 924 integrate biological and agronomic sensitivity (Agriculture) with the rigor of mechanical design
 925 (Engineering) and the power of digital systems (Computer Science). This technical synergy
 926 validates the C-Lab as the natural environment for the evolution towards Biosystems
 927 Engineering, allowing diverse knowledge to converge on real-world problems that none of
 928 the three disciplines could solve in isolation.

- 929 • *Relational Value Beyond the Product*: despite some reservations expressed by company
930 tutors regarding the immediate "innovation readiness" of the results (perceived as not yet
931 mature for industrial application), all companies rated the quality of the process and the
932 collaboration with the University extremely positively. This data demonstrates that the value
933 of the C-Lab for the agri-tech industry lies in co-creation and talent scouting: companies seek
934 direct contact with future designers and managers of agricultural technology.
- 935 • *Coordinating Role of Agricultural Engineering*: the students' willingness to repeat the
936 experience confirms that the model meets a latent demand for hybrid skills. In this context,
937 Agricultural Engineering assumes the role of a strategic "glue," proving to be the only
938 discipline capable of translating IT and engineering innovations within the constraints and
939 needs of the agricultural world.

941 **5.2 Determinants of Success and Group Dynamics**

942
943 The analysis of performance and interactions within the teams revealed crucial evidence for the
944 future design of challenge-based learning initiatives. The data collected suggests that the
945 effectiveness of groups in solving complex industrial challenges is not accidental but is influenced
946 by academic and attitudinal factors that deserve in-depth analysis:

- 947 • *The Value of "Academic Maturity" as a Prerequisite*: the positive correlation between C-
948 Lab performance and indicators, such as average grade and years of attendance,
949 highlights that soft skills do not operate in a vacuum but are more effectively grafted onto
950 solid disciplinary foundations. Academic maturity seems to provide students with the
951 resilience and synthesis skills necessary to manage the ambiguity typical of open-
952 innovation projects. This suggests that, in team composition, the presence of "senior"
953 profiles acts as a stabilizer for group dynamics.
- 954 • *The Paradox of Study Completion*: the negative correlation emerged between the exam
955 completion rate and the final project ranking is of extreme interest. This counter-intuitive
956 data suggests a divergence between the success metrics of the traditional academic
957 curriculum—often focused on mnemonic learning speed and conformity to predefined
958 schemes—and the skills required by the C-Lab. In unstructured industrial contexts, risk
959 propensity, cognitive flexibility, and divergent thinking are necessary; those are qualities
960 that, paradoxically, risk being "eroded" by an excessively rigid study path focused solely
961 on quantitative performance.
- 962 • *Conflict Management and Team Coordination*: Although multi-disciplinarity is the lifeblood
963 of innovation, the results show that it can generate communicative friction and
964 coordination difficulties, if not mediated. The tendency of teams to encounter obstacles in
965 communication with company tutors highlights a linguistic gap between university and
966 industry. This underlines the need to systematically integrate specific training modules on
967 teamwork management and creative problem-solving methodologies, especially within
968 Agricultural Engineering curricula.

969 970 **5.3 Implications for Agricultural Engineering and Academic Policy Recommendations**

971
972 To reverse the marginalization of Agricultural Engineering and recover the necessary dialogue
973 with Engineering and Computer Science departments, the Contamination Lab model must not be
974 interpreted as an isolated or one-off event. On the contrary, it must evolve into a permanent and
975 structured institutional tool. Based on the evidence collected, it is recommended that universities
976 hosting both agricultural and engineering-technological departments formally adopt this model,
977 focusing on three strategic directions:

- 978 • *Synchronization of Languages and "Disciplinary Diplomacy"*: the C-Lab serves as a
979 training ground for future Biosystems Engineering graduates, allowing them to perform
980 the necessary synthesis between the metrological and technical rigour, typical of
981 engineers, and the biological and environmental complexity, inherent to agronomists. This

982 "synchronization" is the only way to heal the historical Italian academic misalignment: the
 983 C-Lab forces different areas to converge on a common object (the machine, the sensor,
 984 the process), transforming the bureaucratic barriers of SSDs into permeable boundaries
 985 for intellectual exchange.

- 986 • *Evolution of the Corporate Role: From Client to Co-creator*: critical feedback received from
 987 tutors highlights a fundamental policy lesson: the success of hybridization depends not
 988 only on the university but also on the maturity of the industrial partner. It is necessary to
 989 train corporate mentors so they move beyond the logic of "request for a supply/advice"
 990 and embrace that of a "collaborative research." Universities should promote the C-Lab as
 991 an Open Innovation environment where the company does not limit itself to evaluating a
 992 result, but actively participates in the training of the very hybrid profiles it claims to need.
- 993 • *Formalization in Study Paths*: to maximize impact, it is suggested to integrate the C-Lab
 994 not as an extracurricular activity, but as an accredited optional module (with ECTS/CFU)
 995 or as a preparatory phase for the degree thesis (related to a compulsory qualification).
 996 This would give academic dignity to the "contamination" activities and encourage the
 997 brightest students to invest time in projects that, while risky and unstructured, represent
 998 the true frontier of employability in agri-tech 4.0.

1000 5.4 Study Limitations and Possible Future Evolution

1001
 1002 Despite the interesting evidences from the obtained results, this study has some methodological
 1003 limits that pave the way for necessary future investigations, and evidences some possible
 1004 refinements of the proposed model:

- 1005 • *Large-scale Validation*: future research developments should include monitoring multiple
 1006 editions of the C-Lab and comparing different universities. This will confirm whether the
 1007 "study completion paradox" and the correlation with academic maturity are structural
 1008 phenomena of the Italian university system or linked to the specific local context.
- 1009 • *Transition to the Thematic Model*: the natural evolution of the proposed format involves
 1010 moving from an "open" approach to vertical Thematic C-Labs. Although this new format
 1011 is not free from potential problems (Tab. 5), pre-defining priority technological areas—
 1012 such as the development of agricultural robotics, the integration of new materials for agri-
 1013 tech, or the application of AI and Big Data in crop monitoring—would allow for the
 1014 attraction of industrial partners with more homogeneous technical challenges. This
 1015 approach would foster deeper scientific convergence between Agriculture, Engineering,
 1016 and Computer Science departments, bringing the solutions designed by students closer
 1017 to the industrial prototyping phase.

1018
 1019 **Table 5.** Pros and Cons of a thematic model for the future C-Lab.

Aspect	Pros	Cons
Strategic Thematic Framing	Creates coherence across activities; aligns with long-term research themes	Reduces flexibility; may exclude emerging or interdisciplinary topics
Company Engagement	Facilitates deeper, more strategic partnerships with companies in relevant sectors	Limits involvement of companies from outside the thematic area
Academic Involvement	Enables targeted involvement of experts; easier coordination across departments	May side-line researchers not directly aligned with the selected topic
Student Orientation	Helps students understand expectations and relevance of their participation	May discourage students with unrelated backgrounds from applying
Employment Matching	Improves alignment between student skills and labour market opportunities	Risk of narrowing exposure to only a segment of the agri-tech sector
Participation Diversity	Enhances clarity of the lab's objectives and attracts students with strong motivation	Potential reduction in interdisciplinary richness and spontaneity

1021 5.5 Final remarks

1022
 1023
 1024 The Udine experience validates the C-Lab as a general organizational model capable of

1025 transforming a structural limit into a strategic advantage, creating an ecosystem where, the
1026 hybridization of more than a subject (in this case: agricultural, engineering, and IT skills) produces
1027 a value greater than the sum of the individual disciplines. In comparison to traditional capstone
1028 courses or internships, C-Labs offer greater flexibility, transdisciplinarity, and autonomy for
1029 students, while also delivering tangible value to external stakeholders. From a pedagogical point
1030 of view, after this experience, it is also possible to formulate the following reflection: to prevent
1031 the progress of an academic career from reducing students' mental flexibility, it is essential to
1032 introduce also contamination experiences early on. A contamination lab is thus confirmed as an
1033 essential tool for "training" the ability to apply technical rigor to fluid problems, preparing future
1034 graduates for the real challenges, in particular in the agri-tech sector. As such, C-Labs represent
1035 a powerful tool to revitalize the teaching and perception of Agricultural Engineering in Italy, helping
1036 to attract diverse student profiles, stimulate entrepreneurial initiatives in agri-tech, and align
1037 academic training with the innovation dynamics of real-world agri-food systems. Therefore, the
1038 C-Lab Udine offers Agricultural Engineering the opportunity to reclaim its centrality: no longer a
1039 "niche" sector between two distant areas, but the centre of gravity around which technological
1040 innovation for sustainability and food security revolves. It can be seen as a concrete response to
1041 the need for a new paradigm for Agricultural Engineering in Italy. The evolution towards a more
1042 structured, thematic, and institutionalized format will allow this discipline to emerge from its
1043 academic "shadow zone" to assume a strategic coordinating role. By transforming the current
1044 difficult positioning into a competitive advantage, Agricultural Engineering can become the true
1045 catalyst for Italian agro-industrial innovation, capable of governing the complexity of the ecological
1046 and digital transition through the skillful synthesis of diverse knowledge.

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Author Contributions

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1052 investigation, M.B. and A.B.; resources, M.B. and A.B.; data curation, M.B.; writing—original draft
1053 preparation, M.B. and A.B.; writing—review and editing, M.B. and A.B.; visualization, M.B.;
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1057

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1079

1080

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1083 to publish the results.

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Abbreviations

1086 The following abbreviations are used in this manuscript:

- 1087 • ABET Accrediting Board for Engineering and Technology
- 1088 • AIIA Italian Association of Agricultural Engineering (it. Associazione Italiana di
1089 Ingegneria Agraria)
- 1090 • ASABE American Society of Agricultural and Biological Engineers
- 1091 • BSc Bachelor of Science
- 1092 • CAP Common Agricultural Policy
- 1093 • CFU University learning credits (it. Crediti Formativi Universitari)
- 1094 • CLab Contamination Lab
- 1095 • CREA (Italian) Council for Agricultural Research and Economics (it. Consiglio per la
1096 Ricerca in Agricoltura e l'Analisi dell'Economia Agraria)
- 1097 • CUP Univocal Project Code (it. Codice unico di progetto)
- 1098 • DI4A Department of Agri-Food, Environmental and Animal Sciences of UniUD
- 1099 • DMIF Department of Mathematics, Computer Science and Physics of UniUD
- 1100 • DPIA Polytechnic Department of Engineering and Architecture of UniUD
- 1101 • ECTS
- 1102 • ECTS European Credit Transfer System
- 1103 • EPFL (Swiss) Polytechnic Federal School of Lausanne (fr. École Polytechnique
1104 Fédérale de Lausanne)
- 1105 • ERDF European Regional Development Fund
- 1106 • ESF European Structural Funds
- 1107 • EU European Union
- 1108 • FabLab Fabrication Laboratory
- 1109 • FSC (Italian) Development and Cohesion Fund (it. Fondo Sociale di Coesione)
- 1110 • HIT Innovation hub of Trentino (it. Hub Innovazione Trentino)
- 1111 • ICT
- 1112 • INEST interconnected North East
- 1113 • LM-XX Italian codification for Master's degree courses
- 1114 • L-XX Italian codification for Bachelor's degree courses
- 1115 • MIUR (Italian) Education, University and Research Ministry (it. Ministero dell'Istruzione
1116 dell'Università e della Ricerca)
- 1117 • MSc Master of Science
- 1118 • MUR (Italian) University and Research Ministry (it. Ministero dell'Università e della
1119 Ricerca)
- 1120 • PhD Philosophiæ Doctor
- 1121 • PNRR (Italian) National Recovery and Resilience Plan (it. Piano Nazionale di
1122 Recovery and Resilience)
- 1123 • PoliMI Polytechnic of Milan
- PoliTO Polytechnic of Turin

- 1124 • PR FESR Projects on the European Regional Development Fund (it. Fondo europeo
- 1125 di sviluppo regionale)
- 1126 • R&D Research and Development
- 1127 • SMEs Small and Medium Enterprise
- 1128 • SSD Scientific-Disciplinary Sector
- 1129 • TRIZ Theory of Inventive Problem Solving (ru. Teorija Rešenija Izobretatel'skich Zadač)
- 1130 • UniMAP Universiti Malaysia Perlis
- 1131 • UniUD University of Udine

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